
Manual for the Shiny Application

This manual is based on Version 1.0 of the Shiny Application 'Find Optimal Timing of Samples using Beta Distribution'. We are currently in active development and therefore provide a disclaimer that you might face different issues throughout the use of the application and invite you to report feedback, improvement ideas or bugs to stefan.embacher@medunigraz.at.

General remarks

This framework is only applicable if you expect an initial increase in antibody concentration, followed by a decay. We assume that the antibody concentration stabilizes at a plateau with no further decay, which is a modelling simplification used at the stage of study design. Further, the omission of a lag after exposure (we assume an immediate increase) or that sampling times are provided up to two decimal places are unrealistic assumptions.

The framework asks for five initial information and you need to provide all five, there is no possibility to leave one out. Our framework optimizes three or four sampling times, depending on your choice of the baseline concentration.

We believe that days are the most reasonable time scale, however, the framework is usable on other time scales as well. Further, the approach is not limited to specific antibodies, provided their kinetics follow the assumed functional form. Initial information can be informed by literature, from numerically reported values, derived from equations or extracted from figures, and should be critically evaluated against expert knowledge. If numerical issues arise, we recommend to slightly adjust the input parameters.

In the following, we provide a step-by-step guide of the input parameters, highlighting practical recommendations and key implications, where relevant.

Input

The panel on the left side of the Shiny Application is used to specify the input and consists of a total of 5 tabs, which are described step by step in more detail in the following.

1. Initial Information

The '**Initial Information**' tab requires five obligatory key inputs:

- **Baseline Concentration (A_0)**

This specifies the antibody concentration at time $t = 0$. Please be aware that the choice of $A_0 = 0$ implies 3 samples, while the choice of $A_0 \neq 0$ implies 4 samples. We recommend

to set $A_0 = 0$ only in the case you are sure that you face naïve patients. Otherwise a non-zero A_0 is recommended.

- **Time of Maximum (t_{\max})**

Specifies when the maximum antibody concentration occurs.

- **Maximum Concentration (A_{\max})**

The (mean) maximum antibody concentration.

- **Plateau Concentration (A_{plat})**

The mean antibody concentration when reaching a steady state. Choose a reasonable value, e.g., the lower limit of detection (LLOD), LLOD/2 or a specific value, where the decay becomes very slow. Based on the results of your robustness analysis, we recommend to choose a non-zero value. Note: This is a modelling simplification.

- **Time of the Plateau (t_{plat})**

Specifies when the plateau is reached. The choice of t_{plat} has an effect on the time limits, since it specifies the default upper limit.

2. Enter Variability

The tab '**Enter Variability**' requires input on the variability. The variance-covariance matrix follows an AR(1) structure where:

- σ (standard deviation) and ρ (correlation) are assumed to be known.
- These values (for now) do not affect optimal sampling times.
- They do affect numerical stability and convergence.

3. Options for Optimal Design

In the tab '**Options for Optimal Design**' one can specify restrictions on the sampling times.

- Lower limit: Default is Day 0.
- Upper limit: Default is t_{plat} .
- Key considerations:
 - Ranges adjust based on the value of t_{plat} .
 - The used algorithm does not enforce ordered sampling times.

-
- * If restrictions are not properly set, time points may switch. For example: If the first sampling time is between Day 14-28 and the second is unrestricted, results could be $t_1 = 28$, $t_2 = 0$. We highly recommend to either restrict no sampling time, or all sampling times in an increasing order.
 - * If $A_0 = 0$, restrictions on the fourth time window have no effect.
 - * If starting values fall outside the set limits, the starting values are adjusted to the closest allowed value.

4. Plot Options

Regarding the tab '**Plot Options**': If the checkboxes are ticked, the limits set apply to the displayed plot. There are two checkboxes, one for the x-axis and one for the y-axis.

5. Default Settings

In the tab '**Default Settings**' there are currently two optional settings: The first one is the display length of the plateau, which is called 'x-axis tolerance'. If the x-axis limits are set manually this value is ignored. The second one specifies the extra space shown above the y-axis maximum, unless the limits are specified by the user. The y-axis tolerance is the proportion of the maximum additionally display.

Output

The output section of the Shiny application consists of three parts/panels.

- The first part provides a visualisation of the curve derived from the assumptions made through the input and the resulting beta distribution, while the resulting optimal sampling times are displayed as the dashed red lines.
- The second part highlights the key input parameters and displays the resulting optimal sampling times numerically. Additionally, the user can copy the input and the results to the clipboard for further use. In addition to the displayed values, all others, including input on variability, time restrictions and the resulting beta parameters, are also copied to ensure reproducibility.
- The third part contains a comprehensive text summary of all relevant information, formatted for convenient sharing. Users can copy this summary for collaboration with colleagues or for direct inclusion in publications, ensuring transparency and reproducibility of the results.